

INTANGIBLE CULTURAL HERITAGE: FROM SOCIAL PRACTICE TO PROFESSIONAL ART FORM

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Abstract:

This article analyzes the forms of existence of intangible cultural heritage in society from the point of view of social practice and professional tradition. The study systematically analyzes sources on the intangible cultural heritage of Uzbekistan (descriptive, historical-ethnographic, systematized scientific publications, sources on professional and performing traditions). Also, descriptive and analytical approaches to the study of intangible cultural heritage are compared, and the criteria for the formation of professional traditions, their interaction with social practices, and transformation processes are revealed. In particular, the differences between social practice and professional tradition and their inextricable connection are scientifically substantiated in the case of the tradition of saying "alla", Uzbek dance art, and festive ceremonies. The article concludes that intangible cultural heritage constitutes a continuous chain of development from socially rooted mass practices to forms approaching professional art, and that the relationship between these two forms is determined not by rigid boundaries, but by a process of constant interaction and development.

Keywords: intangible cultural heritage, social practice, professional tradition, cultural practices, professionalization, mentor-disciple system, performing arts.

Intangible cultural heritage is one of the central concepts of modern cultural studies, sociology and the humanities. It is interpreted as a complex phenomenon that embodies the historical memory, social experience, moral values and aesthetic thinking of society. The Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage (2003) adopted by UNESCO defines intangible cultural heritage as a phenomenon that is transmitted from generation to generation through customs, rituals, performing arts, traditional knowledge and skills and plays an important role in the self-understanding of society

[5, p. 2]. However, in the practice of scientific research, it is often observed that intangible cultural heritage is interpreted as a phenomenon that is structurally uniform, without internal levels. In practice, elements of intangible cultural heritage do not exist in society to the same extent and in the same form. Some cultural practices are deeply embedded in everyday social life and are carried out naturally by almost all members of society. Another part, requiring special knowledge, skills and training, is preserved only by representatives of a certain circle as a professional tradition. This difference creates the need to reconsider the social nature of intangible cultural heritage and the forms of its real existence in society.

An analysis of the literature on the issue of scientific research of intangible cultural heritage shows that in foreign cultural studies, serious attention is paid to the issue of the hierarchical structure of this phenomenon. In particular, P. Bourdieu's theory of practice [2], Ya. Assman's concept of cultural memory [4] and D. Noyes's research on the theory of tradition [3] created important methodological foundations that allow analyzing intangible cultural heritage at social levels. The works of Uzbek researchers M. Jurayev on folklore and ethnography [6], Sh. Turdiyev's research on the classification of intangible cultural heritage [15] served to form this area in the national scientific tradition.

From this point of view, this article analyzes intangible cultural heritage as a process from socially rooted practices to professional art forms. The main goal of the study is to identify the forms of existence of cultural practices in society based on sources related to the intangible cultural heritage of Uzbekistan, to differentiate them by social and professional levels, and to scientifically substantiate the internal structure of intangible cultural heritage.

Theoretical and methodological foundations of the study of intangible cultural heritage.

Scientific research of intangible cultural heritage requires, first of all, the identification of a set of sources reflecting this phenomenon and the assessment of their scientific potential. Since intangible cultural heritage does not have a direct material form, the sources used in its study are also not the same in terms of form, content and methodological approach. Therefore, a systematic classification of sources related to intangible cultural heritage is one of the important stages of research.

Sources related to the intangible cultural heritage of Uzbekistan can be divided into several main groups. The first group consists of descriptive sources. In these sources, customs, rituals, folk practices and forms of performance are described mainly by observation and recording. Their main task is to preserve the existing state of cultural practice, and these sources reflect the real-life form of intangible cultural heritage. However, in these types of sources, the social level or professional complexity of phenomena is often not specifically analyzed.

The second group consists of historical-ethnographic sources. These sources highlight elements of intangible cultural heritage in relation to a specific historical period and social environment. In the studies of Uzbek ethnographers [8; 11], rituals, customs, and traditional knowledge are interpreted in close connection with the social structure, economic activity, and worldview of society. These types of sources allow us to study intangible cultural heritage not as a static phenomenon, but as a historical process.

The third group is made up of systematized scientific publications. In such sources, elements of intangible cultural heritage are presented in a concentrated and grouped manner based on certain criteria. The collection "Intangible Cultural Heritage of Uzbekistan" [1], published in 2017, is one of such sources, in which rituals, performance forms, traditional knowledge, and types of crafts are recorded within the framework of one space. The scientific significance of this source is that it creates a general picture of cultural practices, not individual phenomena, and allows them to be compared.

The fourth group includes sources on professional and performing traditions. In these sources, intangible cultural heritage is interpreted not as a social practice, but as a professional activity requiring special knowledge, skills and training. Master-student relations, performance laws and aesthetic norms are the main objects of analysis of these sources. In particular, studies devoted to the traditions of composition and maqom performance in Uzbekistan [7; 13] are of great importance in revealing the mechanisms of formation of professional traditions.

There are two main methodological approaches to the study of intangible cultural heritage: descriptive and analytical approaches. The descriptive approach is aimed at recording cultural practice, describing its external signs and documenting its existing form. Although this approach is important in collecting empirical material, it has limited possibilities in revealing the internal structure of the phenomenon.

The analytical approach involves studying the elements of intangible cultural heritage from the point of view of their social function, level of performance and transmission mechanisms. As P. Bourdieu emphasizes in his theory of practice, "practice has its own logic, different from the logic of logicians" [2, p. 82]. This idea indicates the need to analyze intangible heritage not only as a "text" or "event", but also through the internal logic of practice - the social field, professional discipline and transmission mechanisms. It is the analytical approach that makes it possible to distinguish intangible cultural heritage as a social practice and a professional tradition.

Forms of intangible cultural heritage as a social practice.

Forms of intangible cultural heritage as social practices are an integral part of the life of society, manifested through everyday relationships, family customs and collective experience. As D. Noyes notes, "tradition, folklore or intangible heritage ... originates from communities and is therefore

considered to belong to them" [3, p. 2]. This approach serves to substantiate the mass and collective nature of social practices.

An analysis of materials on the intangible cultural heritage of Uzbekistan shows that some cultural practices have a form of natural transmission in everyday social environments, without a special teaching system. In particular, the mechanism of transmission of "alla" is of such a nature that the skill of performing is passed on from generation to generation informally: "The skill of singing "alla" is a natural inheritance passed on from mothers to daughters, and is not specifically taught to sing it" [1, p. 35]. This example gives a scientific sign of the "social practice" layer: the carrier of the practice is wide, the method of transmission is informal and associated with everyday practice.

Life cycle rituals, family customs and seasonal traditions exist mainly as social practices. Rituals associated with birth, marriage and death are performed by almost all members of society and their performance does not require special training. Ethnographic studies note that "in Uzbek families, rituals associated with the birth of a child, such as "cradle wedding", "hair cutting", are performed in each family, within its own capabilities and customs" [9, p. 78].

Speaking about the popularity of community holidays and seasonal traditions, experts in the field cite the following information: "The most popular of the holidays are Navruz, Ramadan and Kurban Bayit ... where the sick and the elderly are informed" [1, p. 126]. This indicates the social function of holiday practice, solidarity, "inquiry about the well-being", social care and the existence of a seasonal-ritual system.

Ritual practices form social stratification and order through symbolic separation from everyday life. Ya. Assmann clearly defines this situation: "Rituals are actions that are symbolically formed, separated from everyday life" [4, p. 26]. This definition determines the scientific criterion for the concept of social practices: they are not simple habits or repetitive behavior, but actions that strengthen the social structure and activate collective memory through symbolic separation.

The stability of social practices is determined by their inextricable connection with everyday life. At the same time, it is this feature that makes them resistant to external influences. As M. Jorayev notes, "folk traditions and rituals have been refined over the centuries, adapting to the needs of society, and therefore their main content has been preserved stably" [6, p. 43].

Forms of intangible cultural heritage as professional traditions.

Forms of intangible cultural heritage as professional traditions are qualitatively different from practices with social roots. If social practices are carried out by the general public, within the framework of everyday life and without special training, professional traditions require a high level of specialization, continuous education and strict performance criteria. Therefore, professional traditions

constitute a separate level of intangible cultural heritage, which is manifested as an intermediate stage between mass customs and professional art.

The criteria for professionalization of a professional tradition are determined by the laws of performing activities, their internal systematization and the need for special training. An analysis of intangible cultural heritage practices recorded in Uzbekistan shows that complex forms of performance and traditional types of art are formed within the framework of professional traditions. In particular, in the case of Uzbek dance art, it is noted that the performance process is subject to clear norms: "Uzbek dance art is based on a clear rhythm (method) ... dance movements are systematized based on rhythm changes" [1, p. 174]. This fact confirms the existence of important features that distinguish a professional form - systematicity, normativity and performance discipline.

An analysis of sources on the intangible cultural heritage of Uzbekistan shows that professional traditions are formed, first of all, in cultural practices related to performing activities. These include traditional music, oral epic creation, complex stage or ceremonial forms of performance. The art of makom performance occupies a special place in this regard. As T. Gafurbekov's research emphasizes, "makom performance is a complex professional art acquired as a result of many years of hard work, based on the teacher-student system" [7, p. 112].

In professional traditions, the ratio between criteria and variability is of particular importance. In social practices, variability is wide, and there are no strict requirements for the individual behavior of the performer. In professional traditions, performance is subject to certain laws. However, this does not mean absolute rigidity. According to sources, although individual style and improvisation are present in professional performance forms, they should not violate the basic structure of the tradition [1, p. 152]. In this regard, the professional tradition is based on a balance between creative freedom and traditional norms.

Professional traditions are transmitted through the teacher-disciple system. This system includes not only technical skills, but also aesthetic criteria, performance etiquette, and spiritual values. O. Ibrohimov notes that "in traditional music performance, the teacher-student relationship constitutes a complex system of transferring knowledge and experience through personal example, oral instruction, and practical exercises" [10, p. 56].

Professional forms of intangible cultural heritage are preserved by carriers who have a special social status in society. Professional performers and masters are recognized not only as masters of skill, but also as carriers of cultural knowledge. Their activities are often evaluated and recognized by the community, which ensures the stability of professional traditions. At the same time, professional traditions are more prone to transformation than mass social practices and change their form under the influence of historical conditions.

The dynamics of the relationship between social practice and professional tradition. The forms of intangible cultural heritage as social practice and professional tradition are not contradictory, but rather complementary and historically inextricably linked phenomena. Understanding the relationship between these two forms makes it possible to scientifically substantiate the internal structure, development dynamics and functional place of intangible cultural heritage in society.

Social practices constitute the main basic layer of intangible cultural heritage. They are deeply embedded in the process of everyday life and are accepted by members of society as a social norm. Professional traditions are formed precisely on the basis of this mass cultural environment. As Sh. Turdiev noted, "any professional tradition has its roots in folk art and mass practices" [15, p. 89].

Analysis of sources shows that complex forms of performance and types of professional art initially existed as part of social practices, but over time they separated from them and became specialized forms of activity. This process can be interpreted as a process of professionalization. In the process of professionalization, certain elements of social practice are selected, stabilized, and reworked based on aesthetic criteria. As a result, in contrast to mass practice, the quality of performance, technical perfection, and canonized forms take precedence in professional tradition.

However, there are no strict boundaries between these two forms. On the contrary, there is a constant interaction between them. Professional traditions draw inspiration from social practices, relying on their substantive and symbolic foundations. At the same time, professional performance forms can be re-integrated into the social environment over time and become part of the mass cultural experience. This process shows that intangible cultural heritage is in constant motion and that it is not a fixed, unchanging system.

Sources show that in festive practices, along with the "social" layer, there is also a "normative (textual)" layer. In particular, within the framework of the Eid rituals, a religious-legal argument is found: "Every nation has its holiday, this is our holiday" [1, p. 148]. This example shows that the holiday practice exists not only as a collective experience, but also as a ritual system strengthened by normative-textual legitimation.

Historically, some cultural practices were initially associated with social needs, but later rose to the level of a professional tradition. For example, the art of bakhshi, while initially a widespread example of oral creativity among the people, later turned into a complex professional tradition. As noted in the research of H. Zaripov, "the activity of bakhshis is not only the performance of epics, but also a complex creative process requiring special training, performing skills and artistic thinking" [12, p. 34].

In other cases, professional forms partially lost their social function and began to perform mainly an aesthetic or stage function. This situation means that the role of intangible cultural heritage

elements in society changes over time. In modern conditions, many traditional performance forms are adapting to concert-stage practice and acquiring new functional content [14, p. 67].

Conclusion:

The results of the study show that intangible cultural heritage is not a single phenomenon in terms of content, but a multi-level system existing in the forms of social practice and professional traditions. Analyzing intangible cultural heritage through the prism of these two forms allows us to more clearly understand its internal structure, reveal the historical and modern dynamics of cultural processes, and also scientifically substantiate the real functional status of intangible cultural heritage in the life of society.

Socially rooted practices are associated with the everyday life and collective memory of society and ensure the stability of intangible cultural heritage. They exist by the general public, without special training and through informal transmission mechanisms. Family customs, life cycle rituals, and seasonal traditions are typical examples of social practices.

Professional traditions represent a layer of intangible cultural heritage that has become closer to art through a high level of specialization, aesthetic norms, and a mentor-disciple system. They require special knowledge, skills and training and are preserved by carriers with a special social status. Traditional music, maqom performance, and the art of bakhshi are vivid examples of professional traditions.

The relationship between these two forms is determined not by rigid boundaries, but by a continuous process of development. Social practices serve as the basis for professional traditions, and professional traditions, in turn, influence and enrich social practices. Analyzing intangible cultural heritage on the basis of forms of existence allows us to understand its internal structure and scientifically illuminate the dynamics of cultural processes. This approach serves to interpret intangible cultural heritage not as a set of separate types, but as a complex, multi-level cultural system.

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